

Evaluation of Strengthening Character Education in Sd Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District, Serang Regency

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Abstract:- This study focuses on (1) evaluating (context) the vision and mission, formal foundation, needs analysis, and school culture in implementing character education strengthening (PPK), (2) evaluating (input) readiness of character education strengthening program (PPK), school principals, educators, students, curriculum, financing, facilities and infrastructure, parental support (input) (3) Evaluating (process) extracurricular, extracurricular activities, supervision (supervision) This study describes the evaluation of character education strengthening programs (PPK) in SD Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District, Serang Regency. This study uses the CIPP model program evaluation research (context, input, process, product) qualitative method with a descriptive approach. Data collection techniques, observation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is an effort taken by humans to acquire knowledge which is then used as the basis for attitude and behavior. Therefore, education is one of the processes of forming human character. In the whole process carried out by humans, an educational process will produce attitudes and behaviors that eventually become the character, personality, or character. (Undang-Undang No. 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional) States that "Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious, spiritual strength, self-control, personality, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, the community, nation, and state."

The role of education is significant in shaping the character of the Indonesian nation to be the capital to face every challenge in an era that continues to change. Education should form intelligent and characterized human beings to create superior national human resources (Aningsih et al., 2022). As long as the nation wants to exist and continues to exist, strengthening character education must be an integrated part of generational education. National Education System. The transformation of Indonesia's national education can be started by putting the nation's character back as the most profound spirit of national education and intellectuality reflected in the competencies possessed (Yustitia et al., 2021).

On February 10, 2019, news circulated that should not happen in the world of education; a junior high school teacher made fun of by his students in class, after bullying the teacher was seen in a video of students smoking in

class (Witri Nasuha, 2019). This news is unfortunate When a student has no respect and even dares to bully his teacher.

Mazzola survey results in (Yahiji & Damhuri, 2018) that (1) every day about 160,000 students get bullied at school, 1 out of 3 respondents ages studied (students aged 18 years) have experienced acts of violence, 75-80% of students have observed acts of violence, 15-35% of students are victims of cyber violence.

Juvenile delinquency. KPAI stated that violence between students in 2012 reached 147 cases (Indonesian Review, 2015). Meanwhile, the chairman of KOMNAS PA noted that 128 cases of brawls occurred in 2012 (Beritasatu, 2013). In 2013 cases of violence between students increased to 255 cases, 20 of them died (Indonesian Review, 2015), and brawl cases increased to 229 cases (Beritasatu, 2013). In 2014 cases of violence between students again increased to 2,737 cases (Indonesian Review, 2015) (Syifaunnufush & Diana, 2017).

Various multi-dimensional crises in Indonesia show that this nation is not doing well. Thomas Lickona in (Ririn, 2018) that a nation is on the verge of collapse if it has the following ten signs: (1) increased violence among youth (2) use of foul language and words (3) peer-group substantial influence in violent acts (4) increased behavior self-destructive, such as the use of drugs, alcohol and free sex (5) the blurring of good and evil moral guidelines (6) a decrease in work ethic, a shared sense of responsibility for individuals and citizens, (9) a culture of dishonesty (1) a sense of mutual suspicion and hatred among each other.

These ten signs are signs of the nation's destruction, indicating to us the importance of implementing strengthening character education in providing education and learning. According to (Subianto, 2013) "School, in essence, is not just a place for "transfer of knowledge." Fraenkel (1977: 1-2) stated that schools are not merely places where teachers convey knowledge through various subjects. Schools are also institutions that strive for value-oriented enterprises and learning processes." It is necessary to have a character strengthening movement integrated into the learning process and quality improvement through school culture (Setiawan et al., 2021).

Character is necessary to face the challenges of the constantly evolving times. One of the efforts made by the government is strengthening character education (PPK) which is integrated into the National Mental Revolution Movement (GNRM). Strengthening Character Education (PPK) is an Education Movement in schools to strengthen

students' character through harmonization (Utomo et al., 2021).

Strengthening character education is an essential aspect in developing the affective domain. According to Sharif (Islam, 2017), To keep up with the times and the education system, the education system must have a dynamic curriculum and undergo systematic changes and sustainable and directed development. In addition to being dynamic and under the needs of education that continues to grow (Auliaty et al., 2021).

The implementation of strengthening character education in schools is necessary. Remembering to overcome various national character crises, the internalization of character values must be cultivated in schools with character. To strengthen the implementation policy of the KDP, the government makes juridical bases such as RI Law Number 17 of 2007 concerning RPJPN 2005-2025, RI Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education in formal education units, up to the regulation of the director-general of primary and secondary education Number: 097/D/HK/2019 concerning technical guidelines for strengthening character education (Wahyudiana et al., 2021).

In (Peraturan Presiden Republik Indonesia Nomor 87 Tahun 2017 Tentang Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter, 2017) in the transitional provisions of article (16) confirms that "Education units that have not implemented PPK or that have implemented KDP but are not yet under this presidential regulation, within a maximum period of 2 (two) years must adjust to this presidential regulation". This rule was set on September 6, 2017, by the President of the Republic of Indonesia; in other words, on September 6, 2019, this regulation had to be adjusted by the Education unit (Irawan & Iasha, 2021).

Inner son (Andrianto, 2021) Program evaluation is an effort to collect, compile, process, and analyze facts, data, and information to conclude prices, values, achievements, uses, benefits regarding a program, office, school, organization, or institution and others to be concluded as a basis for making decisions. Decisions about whether the program should be continued, revised or discontinued". This study used program evaluation research with the CIPP model (context, input, process, and output). Stufflebeam developed this model (Rachamatika et al., 2021).

Kareo Elementary School, Jawilan District, Serang Regency is an education unit that has implemented character education strengthening (PPK) in its education unit since 2017, several adjustments to character education strengthening at Kareo Elementary School, Jawilan District were made to achieve the expected strengthening of character education, this makes Researchers are interested in researching evaluating character education programs at SD Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District, some considerations are to see and evaluate the management of strengthening character education (PPK). The results of this evaluation

are used as feedback for schools, policymakers, and researchers themselves. The evaluation aims to obtain the correct information for consideration and measure the extent to which what was previously planned has been achieved.

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II. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with the evaluation research program CIPP model (Contexts, input, process, product). This study looks at the social reality in the field regarding strengthening character education in SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Jawilan, Kab. Serang. In this study, specific criteria were set to serve as guidelines in conducting research evaluating the character education strengthening program to determine the program's achievements. According to Arikunto (Pelita & Widodo, 2020), Evaluation research aims to determine the achievement of program goals by taking steps to determine program activities because program evaluators want to know which parts of the program components and sub-components have not been implemented and why.

A. Research time and place

The research time took place in August – December 2021 at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answer. Considering that this school has implemented character education strengthening since 2017 since the program was established in the same year, this is a consideration for researchers to see how far the effectiveness of the character education strengthening program has been implemented.

B. Research subject

The research subjects were determined purposively or based on specific considerations, namely schools that strengthened character education. SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. District Headquarters. Serang is a school that implements strengthening character education, with key informants in the school being the principal, teachers, and students.

C. Data analysis technique

Analysis of the data using the interactive analysis model of Miles and Huberman. Data analysis consists of three stages: data reduction, presentation, and conclusion/verification. Data reduction includes summarizing activities, selecting main things, focusing on

essential things to look for themes and patterns, second, presenting data presented in the form of descriptive narratives based on categories to provide a clear and detailed picture. Third, concluding/verification is carried out by testing each selected data's suitability, correctness, and strength through a data validity test.

D. Procedure

Data was collected using interviews, observation, field notes, and documentation techniques. Interviews were conducted with resource persons at schools to determine the context, input, process, and product. Observations were made on several aspects in schools, including (1) observation of the juridical basis of the policy of strengthening character education programs in schools (2) observing suggestions and infrastructure to see the completeness.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. The context of strengthening character education in SD Negeri Kareo

The components of context evaluation are 1) vision and mission 2) formal foundation. The results of the evaluation of the context component in this study, namely regarding the program's legal basis, goals, and objectives. Then the criteria regarding the legal basis, goals, and objectives of the program. The evaluation that has been determined is the suitability of the components, namely (1) the legal basis, (2) the objectives, and (3) the function of the character education strengthening program at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Jalan with guidelines for strengthening character education (PPK).

a) Legal basis for character education strengthening program (PPK)

The legal basis for strengthening character education programs at SD Negeri Kareo

- Law number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system
- Permendiknas number 20 concerning competency standards for elementary and secondary education graduates.
- Presidential regulation number 87 of 2017 concerning strengthening character education.
- Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture No. 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening character education in formal education units.
- Nawacita Agenda No. 8: Strengthening the revolution of the nation's character through character and character building of students as part of the mental revolution. Tri Sakti: Creating a generation with personality in culture.
- RPJMN 2015-2019: "strengthening character education for school-age children at all levels of education to strengthen students' moral values, character, and personality by strengthening characters integrated into subjects.
- Implementation of strengthening character education in SD Negeri KareoJawilandistrict already has a legal basis for implementing the program based on applicable rules.

b) The purpose of strengthening the character education of SD Negeri Kareo

Each school has a goal of implementing education in schools, intending to prepare for every step that will be carried out; SD Negeri Kareo has a goal adjusted to strengthen character education (PPK) based on guidelines. The purpose of strengthening character education is to form a superior generation with good character. Developing good character will encourage students to grow with their capacity and commitment. Based on the documentation results of strengthening character education, it is under the objectives of SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Jawilan, namely: (1) Realizing healthy, intelligent, cultured students, excelling in achievement and having good morals (2) increasing students' activities and learning outcomes in the learning process (3) increasing the professionalism of educators and education staff (4) improving school management transparent, accountable and professional (6) increasing the participation of the community and other stakeholders. (7) increasing the religiosity of students.

The purpose of the program to strengthen the character education of SD Negeri KareoJawilan district is under the guidelines for implementing character education strengthening (PPK), which has the aim of forming the character of students based on the central values of interrelated characters, namely religiosity, nationalism, independence, cooperation, and integrity.

c) Benefits of Strengthening Character Education

Implementation of strengthening character education at SD Negeri KareoJawilan district develops students' potential as described in the guidelines for strengthening character education, namely heart, mind, and sports. Based on the results of an interview with the principal of SD Negeri Kareo, "the benefits of this character education strengthening movement are to shape and develop the attitudes and behavior of students, how to become independent individuals, respect others, have tolerance for differences, become disciplined and responsible individuals to be a provision in people's lives.

Based on the guidelines for strengthening character education, it has the benefits of 1) Strengthening student character education in preparing students' competitiveness with 21st-century competencies, namely: critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration; 2) learning is carried out in an integrated manner at school and outside of school with teacher supervision; 3) revitalizing the role of principals as managers and teachers as PPK inspirations; 4) revitalization of the school committee as a school gotong royong agency and community participation; 5) strengthening the role of the family through a 5-day learning policy; 6) collaboration between K/L,

local government, community institutions, education activists and other sources.

Based on the results of observations made at SD Negeri Kareo, District Headquarters. Attack the benefits and guidelines for strengthening character education.

Based on the results of observations made by researchers during distance learning and offline learning. Researchers make observations by participating in online learning, implementation related to the benefits of strengthening character education can be seen in learning activities that are directed and have the substance of planting character values in students, it is seen from online learning and face-to-face learning, by looking at the tasks

given by educators to students by making habits, such as: praying before and after studying educators instruct both online and offline, students to clean at home as well as what is done when at school when online learning is done by providing video evidence when doing activities and carry out recitations of the Qur'an at home or school, namely a short surah every Tuesday.

Based on the discussion on the components (context) in the character education strengthening program, it can be concluded that these aspects are fulfilled even though there are several obstacles due to the pandemic that occurred. However, it can be seen that the context component (context) is met according to the evaluation criteria.

No	Aspect	Evaluation Criteria and Success Indicators	Achievement of evaluation criteria
1.	Legal Foundation	The legal basis for implementing the character education strengthening program at SDN Kareo is in accordance with the guidelines for implementing character education strengthening	Criteria met
2.	Purpose	Activities in implementing the character education strengthening program at SD Negeri Kareo are in accordance with the guidelines for implementing character education strengthening	Criteria met
3.	Benefit	The benefits of implementing character education strengthening at SD Negeri Kareo have been fulfilled with guidelines for strengthening character education	Partially Fulfilled

Table 1. Achievement of Strengthening Character Education

B. Input Strengthening Character Education of SD Negeri Kareo

Entrance evaluation (input) evaluates 1) program readiness 2) principals 3) Student staff, curriculum, financing, facilities and infrastructure, and parental support. The primary orientation in evaluating inputs (input) is to state what can be achieved and what is desired.

a) school culture

School culture is a shared value that binds togetherness in the school environment. Good school culture can foster a climate that encourages residents in the school environment to learn so that a shared spirit emerges, which always carries out continuous learning that has the value of the common good. According to (Subianto 2013), examples of behaviors can be applied in schools: 1). Familiarize students with a culture of greetings, greetings, and smiles 2). Arriving at school, say hello while shaking hands and kissing the teacher's hand. 3). Greet friends, security guards, canteen salespeople, or school cleaning services 4). Greet guests who come to school politely 5). Familiarize students to speak in a good and polite language 6). Educate students to sit politely in grade 7). Educate students to eat while sitting in the space provided, not while walking 8). Guiding and familiarizing students with Dhuha prayer and Dzuhur prayers in congregation at school

Based on the results of school culture observations seen in implementing the character education strengthening program at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answers are as follows:

The results of observations made by researchers related to school culture before the COVID-19 pandemic both directly and after the pandemic were carried out virtually. The formation of values is seen in activities such as routinely carrying out the dhuha prayer in congregation (before the pandemic), celebrating significant holidays, flag ceremonies every Monday (before the pandemic, carrying out short recitations of surahs, cooperation activities by implementing the Jumsih program (Friday). at clean), as well as the literacy movement to read books 15 minutes before studying and carry out various extracurricular activities carried out by Scouts every Friday, sports held every Saturday (soccer, futsal, sepak takraw, and athletics).

Furthermore, the researchers conducted interviews with school principals, namely "school culture that is under the implementation of strengthening character education is very important to encourage students to excel and familiarize students with character under the expected goals, students show this by following the rules set at school such as wear clothes neatly, meet the teacher and give greetings. Pray before and after and after study.

Then the researchers conducted interviews with teachers about school culture "habituation or implementation of strengthening character education carried out in the Kareo State Elementary School environment such as habituation to carry out routine ceremonies on Mondays can foster a love for the homeland,

do cooperate on Friday clean so that students get used to cooperation and love for the environment. They instilled religious values such as carrying out the dhuha prayer in the congregation and doing short letter recitations. The internalization of values for strengthening character education is expected to become student habituation both in the school environment and outside school.

Based on the results of the data findings, it can be seen that improving the quality through school culture at SD Negeri Kareo is under the guidelines for strengthening character education.

b) Competency of Educators at SD Negeri Kareo

Adequate human resources (HR) are significant to support the implementation of a program to be implemented in the educational environment. The competence of educators in SD Negeri Kareo is an input aspect. Educators who have competence are critical in integrating the values of strengthening character education in learning and habituation in schools.

The strategic role of educators in strengthening character education, Lickona in (Darmayanti& Wibowo, 2014) states that teachers can influence the character of children or students. One of them is to be an example for them. Therefore, educators must understand and implement the movement to strengthen character education. In general, almost all educators know about character education. However, they did not understand the concept of character education in-depth, then the researchers conducted interviews with teachers at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answer.

"It takes time to understand the strengthening of character education to understand the real concept, but in this case, we as educators always try to continue to learn to understand the actual concept in strengthening character education."

Furthermore, the researchers conducted in-depth interviews with teachers. "The quality improvement program through a school culture that was implemented in 2017, is relatively new, it takes time for educators to really understand the concept of Strengthening Character Education (PPK) in-depth and comprehensively, especially from 2020 until now (2021) we are tested with there is a pandemic that has an impact on school culture and we have difficulty integrating character values in learning because it is done virtually so we cannot interact directly with students".

It was strengthening character education in SD Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District was implemented in 2017, so there needs to be adaptation time for educators to really understand and instill values optimally. Through seminars and other training, it can help improve the understanding and competence of educators in understanding the overall character education strengthening program; the pandemic factor also affects educators so that it is difficult to instill the value of strengthening character education in SD Negeri KareoKec. Answer.

Another practical aspect is the example of educators in carrying out learning. Educators show exemplary to students. Based on the results of observations made by researchers by observing learning both online and in person.

"In learning that is carried out online or in person, it is seen that educators carry out learning in a friendly and polite manner. Educators show exemplary. However, it seems that there is still a lack of time discipline, there is a delay from educators in carrying out learning."

It can be concluded that the achievement of the input component of the character education strengthening program at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answer. Partially met the criteria set.

C. *The Process of Strengthening Character Education of SD Negeri Kareo*

Process evaluation, evaluating activities 1) extracurricular 2) extracurricular 3) supervision, program implementation to convey to outsiders and further assist other user parties, who provide opinions on interfering criteria.

a) Implementation

The process of strengthening character education in learning should be planting the character values of students. The integration process of character values is carried out by sorting out appropriate character values; the integration of values for strengthening character education in the lesson plans is done by adding or modifying the components of the lesson plans (learning objectives, methods, and assessment techniques) that can develop the character of the Ministry of National Education in (Darmayanti) & Wibowo, 2014) explains that there are two types of learning experiences that are built, namely through intervention and habituation. Intervention is an atmosphere of learning and learning interaction that is intentionally designed to achieve the goal of character building by implementing structured activities. It means that the movement for strengthening character education needs programmed conditioning. Researchers made observations to determine the learning method used to optimize students' activeness.

Strengthening character education at SD Negeri Kareo has been good, with a pleasant atmosphere between all school residents. Good habits can be seen in school residents who respect each other. When they see the teacher, students spontaneously immediately greet the teacher by saying greetings; the lesson plans guide most educators in carrying out learning in the classroom, and the methods used are excellent and make students active.

Results of interviews with teachers related to lesson plans:

"I always refer to the lesson plan, because in my opinion, we as educators must-have preparation and reference in carrying out the learning process so that it is under what is expected, even though in practice we often adjust to the conditions in the classroom."

Then an interview was conducted with the principal of the school.

"The educators at this Kareo State Elementary School are still in the adjustment period in the character education strengthening program in integrating it with learning. The importance of training and socializing this program is even more so that they can increase their knowledge and abilities in integrating the values of strengthening character education in the classroom".

In readiness for SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answers based on the results of interviews with school principals, namely:

"In terms of curriculum, facilities, and infrastructure, our school is ready to carry out strengthening of character education through improving the quality of school culture; I was a school principal give the task to every teacher to integrate the values of strengthening character education in the syllabus and lesson plans as well as in extracurricular activities at school. We".

Strengthening character education in SD Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District includes strengthening character education (PPK) through learning and habituation in the school environment. Habituation activities in the school environment can be carried out through programmed activities such as extracurricular activities management of strengthening character education at SD Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District is related to school management or management. Management is how the quality culture through strengthening character education is planned (planning), implemented (actuating), and controlled (controlling) in school habituation.

b) Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation are critical to finding out how far a program can run. The results of interviews with school principals regarding monitoring and evaluation carried out "The monitoring and evaluation stage is the stage to determine the achievement of the program itself. The monitoring task is delegated to the school supervisor who will supervise and assist the school directly".

Monitoring and evaluation activities of character education strengthening programs at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Jawilan is done by checking learning tools such as syllabus and lesson plans, but monitoring and evaluating the implementation of strengthening character education at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. The effectiveness of the Jawilan has not been measured by the principal of SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answer because the instrument used is not yet available.

c) Accountability

The last stage of the process is the accountability of the school in the form of an accountability report on the implementation of the character education strengthening program, while the teacher's responsibility in the character education strengthening program is in the form of a report on the assessment of student attitudes during character education strengthening.

Most teachers have implemented character values but do not have written records regarding student observations. This oral assessment is very weak to be used as a basis for consideration in determining student profile conclusions.

Following are the interviews with teachers regarding the absence of written documents on character values. "Indeed, there is no written documentation, but in practice, the values of strengthening character education have been instilled in students both in classroom learning and in extracurricular activities."

Overall, the achievement of the process component of strengthening character education at SD Negeri Kareo, Jawilan District, can be concluded to be partially fulfilled. It is based on 1) the criteria for implementing character education strengthening integrated with learning and the methods used are appropriate (2) monitoring and evaluation carried out by the Education office through school supervisors have been carried out (3) Accountability, no written report or physical evidence of results assessment of attitudes towards the character values of students.

No	Aspect	Criteria	Achievement of criteria
1.	Implementation	There is a match between the implementation procedures for strengthening character education in schools and guidelines for implementing character education strengthening	Multiple evaluation criteria are met
2.	Monitor and evaluate	The existence of monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of strengthening character education in schools in accordance with the guidelines for the implementation of strengthening character education	Multiple evaluation criteria are met
3.	Accountability	There is a report on the implementation of strengthening character education in schools in accordance with the guidelines for the implementation of strengthening character education	Criteria not met

Table 2. Achievement of Accountability

D. Product of Strengthening Character Education of Kareo State Elementary School

The achievement of the results of the quality culture of strengthening character education at SDN Kareo, Jawilan District, Serang Regency is under the guidelines for implementing character education strengthening. In school

life, since implementing a quality culture through strengthening character education, the discipline of educators and students has begun to appear, such as entering school on time and entering class when recess ends. Likewise, changes are now beginning to appear in the timely flag ceremony.

Based on the results of observations carried out by researchers, it has been seen that there is habituation under character values. Researchers conducted interviews; it was seen that there was an awareness that students were present on time, not cheating when the bell rang they entered the class.

The results of interviews with the principal of SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Jawilanmanhwa "The achievement of the results of strengthening character education is enough to bring changes to our school, although it is not yet at a perfect stage, from a quality culture through strengthening character education, students are more motivated to excel, study harder, and most importantly, life in the school environment becomes fun for them. Learners".

No	Aspect	Criteria	Achievements
1.	Achievement of results	The realization of a school culture based on the values of strengthening character education and student achievement, both academic and non-academic	Evaluation criteria met

Table 3: Achievement of Strengthening Character Education Product

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of the evaluation results of the character education strengthening program at SDN Kareo, Kec. JawilanKab, Serang which includes components of context (context), input (input), process (process), and product (product), the researchers convey conclusions and recommendations as follows:

Evaluation of quality culture through strengthening character education (PPK) at SD Negeri Kareo. The answer that uses the context, input, process, and product (CIPP) model shows the overall achievement of each component in the good or fulfilled category.

Conclusions on each evaluation component can be described as follows:

The context component in the evaluation of the CIPP model program.

- The legal basis is in the category of program criteria met,
- The objectives of the character education strengthening program in the program criteria category are met
- strengthening character education is in the category of criteria Partly fulfilled

A. Component input (input).

- Culture of SD Negeri KareoKec. Jawilan is in the category of program criteria met
- The competence of educators at SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Answers in the program criteria category Partially fulfilled

B. Process components (Process)

- Implementation of Strengthening Character Education in SD Negeri Kareo is in the program category; some evaluation criteria are met
- Monitoring and evaluation of Character Education Strengthening of SD Negeri Kareo is in the category of evaluation criteria; some are met
- Responsibility for Strengthening Character Education of SD Negeri Kareo is in the category of evaluation criteria; some are met.

The product component (product) is the realization of school culture.

Implementation of strengthening the character education of SD Negeri Kareo, Kec. Jawalan is in the category of fulfilled evaluation criteria.

V. RECOMMENDATION

Recommendations that can be formulated based on the conclusions above are as follows:

The existence of regulations largely determines the context component. All citizens must understand these regulations in the school environment so that the program is carried out under the objectives and has benefits. Therefore, it is necessary to have:

- Socialization and training related to the implementation of strengthening character education
- Schools make more understandable guidelines containing instructions for strengthening character education programs

The character education strengthening program aims to develop students' character as human beings who are cultured and have a national character. This goal will be achieved if all aspects function correctly, such as the competence of educators and good school culture. Therefore it is necessary:

- The Department of Education as a stakeholder to conduct training for professional development of educators to improve the competence of educators
- The principal holds regular meetings to discuss the obstacles faced in the implementation of strengthening character education.

It is necessary to do the implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and accountability for strengthening character education; it is necessary to do

- The principal routinely checks the lesson plans and syllabus, directly reviews the learning process, makes school regulations regarding the obligation of educators to report on student observations, and prepares to monitor instruments for strengthening character education.
- Educators, the example of educators must be improved, especially in terms of discipline.

They are strengthening character education by improving the quality culture in SD Negeri Kareo needs to be maintained and is under the values of local wisdom.

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